

Vaccines cause autoimmune diseases: The latest evidence implicates influenza, tetanus, diphtheria, and pertussis (Tdap), human papilloma virus, pneumococcal, hepatitis A, hepatitis B, typhoid, yellow fever, and Japanese encephalitis vaccines in Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD)

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Vanood et al. (1) reviewed case reports implicating influenza, tetanus, diphtheria, and pertussis (Tdap), human papilloma virus, pneumococcal, hepatitis A, hepatitis B, typhoid, yellow fever, and Japanese encephalitis vaccines in Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorders (NMOSD).

Aquaporin-4 (AQP4) is the target self antigen in NMOSD. The role of AQP4 contaminated chick embryo cell culture containing vaccines in the etiology of NMOSD was previously described (2). We have since described the specific immunological mechanism involved in the general phenomena of autoimmunity induced by immunization with homologous xenogeneic antigens (animal/plant/fungal protein containing vaccines) (3). Lambert et al. (4) report that many plant derived foods including corn and soy contain aquaporin proteins which have high homology to human aquaporin. These same plant sources are used to derive growth media and excipients used in vaccine manufacture. Vaccines therefore contain residual proteins from the manufacturing process. Predictably, the administration of these vaccines result in immunization against plant proteins such as AQP4. Antibodies thus synthesized directed against plant AQP4 then cross-react with human self-proteins to induce autoimmune disorders such as NMOSD.

We have previously described the role of plant glutamate receptor protein homology with human self-proteins in numerous autoimmune disorders (5). Glutamate receptors and AQP4 are just two example plant proteins. With thousands of plant proteins contaminating vaccines, one can expect just about every type of autoimmune disease can be initiated by such vaccines (6). Once immunized against such plant proteins, eating such proteins will boost the immune response against self-proteins. In other words, we have autoimmune diseases that are aggravated by foods (7,8). So we have the gut-immune-brain axis. And of course the general case of gut-immune-your-favorite-organ axis.

Immunizing people with animal, plant and fungal proteins is insane and needs to stop immediately. All non-target proteins in vaccines must be removed immediately using processes such as affinity chromatography (9).

References

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